

Calculation of 3-dimensional Integrals(and 2-dimensional Integrals)

Harald Schröer

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First we view the following integrals:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\frac{-c}{2}}^{\frac{c}{2}} \int_{\frac{-b}{2}}^{\frac{b}{2}} \int_{\frac{-a}{2}}^{\frac{a}{2}} g(x_1, x_2, x_3) dx_1 dx_2 dx_3 &= \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \int_0^1 f(x_1, x_2, x_3) dx_1 dx_2 dx_3 \\ &= \lim_{\mu \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^1 f(x_1, \langle \lambda \cdot x_1 \rangle, \langle \mu \cdot x_1 \rangle) dx_1 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

We used the transformation formula see Forster [2] (§§2 and 13) and Corollary 3.2.8(He [3] p.88):

We need the function

$$\vec{A}(x_1, x_2, x_3) = (cx_1 - \frac{c}{2}, bx_2 - \frac{b}{2}, ax_3 - \frac{a}{2})$$

with jacobian matrix

$$D\vec{A}(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \begin{pmatrix} c & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & b & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & a \end{pmatrix}$$

and determinant

$$\det D\vec{A}(x_1, x_2, x_3) = c \cdot b \cdot a.$$

The function f is defined through:

$$f(x_1, x_2, x_3) := a \cdot b \cdot c \cdot g(cx_1 - \frac{c}{2}, bx_2 - \frac{b}{2}, ax_3 - \frac{a}{2})$$

$\langle \ \rangle$ is the fractional part of a number.

We can generalize this idea to every 3-dimensional integral. We view convex combinations, see Barner [1] chapter 13.2 p.30. We construct the function

$$\vec{A}(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \begin{pmatrix} a + x_1 \cdot (b - a) \\ c + x_2 \cdot (d - c) \\ e + x_3 \cdot (f - e) \end{pmatrix}$$

from $[0, 1] \times [0, 1] \times [0, 1]$ to $[a, b] \times [c, d] \times [e, f]$.

We calculate the jacobian matrix:

$$D\vec{A}(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \begin{pmatrix} (b - a) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & (d - c) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & (f - e) \end{pmatrix}$$

with $\det D\vec{A}(x_1, x_2, x_3) = (b - a) \cdot (d - c) \cdot (f - e)$.

Then we have the transformation:

$$\int_a^b \int_c^d \int_e^f g(x_1, x_2, x_3) dx_1 dx_2 dx_3 = \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \int_0^1 f(x_1, x_2, x_3) dx_1 dx_2 dx_3 \quad (2)$$

with

$$f(x_1, x_2, x_3) = |\det D\vec{A}(x_1, x_2, x_3)| \cdot g(\vec{A}(x_1, x_2, x_3))$$

The transformation to an 1-dimensional integral is the same as in equation (1).

For 2-dimensional integrals we need corollary 3.2.5 at He [3].

References

- [1] Martin Barner, Friedrich Flohr "Analysis II" de Gruyter Verlag Berlin 1983
- [2] Otto Forster "Analysis 3" 2.edition Vieweg Verlag Brunswick 1983
- [3] Tian-Xiao He "Dimensionality reducing expansion of multivariate integration" Birkhäuser Verlag Boston 2001